

GraspOS Resource Metadata Schema v1.0

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1. Introduction and Scope

This document is the outcome of the *GraspOS internal Working Group on Resource Metadata Schemas*. The main objective of the group was to define a set of metadata fields that can be used to describe different types of resources relevant to research assessment processes, and that can be used for the development of the *GraspOS infrastructure catalogue*¹. The schema is designed to include basic fields common to general-purpose scholarly catalogues (such as Zenodo² or the EOSC EU Node Resource Hub³), while also providing richer information (a) to better inform on key aspects of each resource that are important to know for using them in practice, and (b) to support resource discoverability within the GraspOS infrastructure by enabling the implementation of advanced filtering features (called “exploration paths”).

The document describes the first, mature version of the metadata schema. Updated versions are possible in the near future.

2. Assumptions and Notations

Four main types of resources are currently supported by the GraspOS infrastructure:

- *Datasets*: raw or structured data that can be used to either directly support the conduction of assessment events or produce indicators, track records, narratives or other evidence that could be valuable in such processes.
- *Tools*: stand-alone pieces of software, such as scripts, executables, libraries, or even workflows, which can be used by installing and executing them locally on a computer or computational cluster owned by the end-user to conduct a particular type of analysis and/or produce data.

¹ GraspOS infrastructure catalogue: <https://graspos-infra.athenarc.gr/catalogue/>

² Zenodo: <https://zenodo.org/>

³ EOSC EU Node Resource Hub: <https://open-science-cloud.ec.europa.eu/resources/all>

- *Services*: pieces of software that provide a set of functions or features for the end user and that are typically hosted on a remote server or cluster and accessed via a Web interface or API. Essentially, the service providers aim to offer them in a 24/7 manner giving guarantees for the respective Quality of Service (QoS), such as the service availability.
- *Templates & Guidelines*: various templates for documents that can be used during the research assessment process (e.g., related to assessment readiness, stakeholder mapping, value and purpose statement), academic CV templates (e.g., Narrative-style CV templates), guideline documents (e.g., OS assessment guide, EDI guide), checklists, and indicator toolboxes.

The metadata schema presented in this document applies to all these resource types, with certain exceptions where specific fields are not relevant to a given type. Every exception is indicated in the respective field record description (see Section 3).

For each field, the document specifies not only its name and a short description, but also its expected data type and whether it is required, optional, or recommended. The distinction between optional and recommended is that recommended fields should ideally not be left empty, as completing them ensures that the resource is well-described and easier to discover. The short description also indicates potential metadata sources. User-provided fields require the GraspOS resource provider to supply the information manually, while in other cases the metadata can be harvested automatically from external sources (e.g., Zenodo or the OpenAIRE Graph).

Finally, an asterisk-based notation is used to indicate whether a field is relevant for the “exploration paths” feature (i.e., advanced filtering) of the GraspOS infrastructure. A single asterisk (*) denotes fields that are central to filtering, while a double asterisk (**) marks fields used in a supporting role (e.g., for ordering results rather than filtering them).

3. Metadata Schema

The following tables present all metadata fields of the GraspOS Resource Metadata Schema, grouped according to their semantic categories.

Basic information

A set of metadata describing basic information of the resource.

Field name	Short description	Data type	Requirement
doi	Digital object identifier representing all versions of the resource. User provided.	string	required ⁴
doi_last	Digital object identifier representing the most recent version of the resource. Can	string	required ⁵

⁴ For all resource types, except services.

⁵ For all resource types, except services.

	be fetched from Zenodo (metadata.doi).		
version	The most recent version of the resource. Can be fetched from Zenodo (metadata.version).	string	required
resource_type	Type of the resource. User provided.	controlled string ⁶	required
title	Title of resource (according to the most recent version). Can be fetched from Zenodo (metadata.title).	string	required
description	Short description of the resource (according to the most recent version). Can be fetched from Zenodo (metadata.description).	text	required
publication_date	Date of publication (of the most recent version) of the resource. Can be fetched from Zenodo (metadata.publication_date).	String - ISO8601 format (YYYY-MM-DD)	required ⁷
access_rights*	The access rights of the resource (according to the most recent version). Can be fetched from Zenodo (metadata.access_right).	controlled string	required
license*	License that applies to the resource (according to the most recent version).	object	required
url	The main URL of the resource (e.g., a landing page providing basic info for the resource). User provided.	string - URL	optional ⁸
creators	The creators of the resource. Can be fetched from Zenodo (metadata.creators).	array of objects	required ⁹
contributors	The contributors of the resource (e.g., editors, curators, etc.). Can be fetched from Zenodo (metadata.contributors).	Array of objects	optional
keywords	Keywords describing topics related to the resource. Can be fetched from Zenodo (metadata.keywords).	array of strings	recommended
language*	The language of the resource. Can be fetched from Zenodo (metadata.language).	controlled string - ISO 639 language code implemented according to BCP 47	recommended

⁶ Can be "Dataset", "Tool", "Service", or "Template / Guidelines".

⁷ For all resource types, except services.

⁸ Required for services.

⁹ For all resource types, except services.

references	List of references. Can be fetched from Zenodo (metadata.references).	array of strings	optional ¹⁰
adopted_standards	Various specifications adopted/implemented by the resource (e.g., FAIR specs, interoperability standards). Multiple values expected for this field. User provided.	array of strings	optional
TRL	The technology readiness level of a tool or service. Can be fetched from a local service catalogue (e.g., the OpenAIRE Service Catalogue) or it can be user provided.	integer	optional ¹¹

Governance, sustainability, and funding

A set of metadata describing information related to the governance, sustainability, and funding of the resource.

Field name	Short description	Data type	Requirement
governance_model	The governance model followed for the particular resource. User provided.	text	optional
governance_bodies	The organisations or structures involved in the governance model. Their roles can be (optionally) explained in the governance_model field. User provided.	array of strings	optional
sustainability_plan	URL of digital document elaborating the sustainability plan of the resource (if available). User provided.	string - URL	optional
funding	Identification information of received funding that contributed to the creation and maintenance of the resource. Can be fetched from Zenodo (metadata.grants).	array of objects	optional

Support

A set of metadata offering useful information for the support options of the respective resource.

Field name	Short description	Data type	Requirement
documentation_urls	URLs to the main documentation websites of the resource. User provided.	array of strings - URLs	recommended
training_materials	URLs to the main pages listing training material for the resource. User provided.	array of strings - URLs	optional

¹⁰ Not applicable for services.

¹¹ Not applicable for datasets and templates & guidelines.

support_channels	Collection of helpdesk emails, forms, and community forum URLs. User provided.	array of strings	recommended
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Coverage

A set of metadata explaining the context under which the resource is useful in research assessment and the various aspects it covers.

Field name	Short description	Data type	Requirement
SCOPE_stages*	The SCOPE methodology stages in which the resource can be used. User provided.	array of controlled strings ¹²	optional
assessment_values*	A set of values that can be supported by a research assessment event using the resource. User provided.	array of strings	optional
assessment_subjects*	The research entities (e.g., individual researchers, research performing organisations, countries, etc.) of which the assessment can be supported using the resource. User provided.	array of controlled strings ¹³	recommended
assessment_functionalities*	Main functionality categories supported by the resource (in case of tools and services). User provided.	array of controlled strings ¹⁴	recommended ¹⁵
evidence_types*	The types of assessment evidence (e.g., narratives, indicators, lists of contributions, badges) that the respective source is offering or leveraging. User provided.	array of controlled strings ¹⁶	optional
geographic_scope*	List of geographical areas that are covered by the specific resource (it may be location-agnostic). User provided.	array of controlled strings	required
covered_fields*	List of scientific fields/topics that are covered by the specific resource (it may be field-agnostic). User provided.	array of strings	required

¹² "Start", "Context", "Options", "Probe", "Evaluate".

¹³ "Researcher", "Research performing organisation", "Country", "Other".

¹⁴ "Scholarly data enrichment: Missing attributes", "Scholarly data enrichment: Indicators", "Scholarly data enrichment: Missing links & semantics", "Open Science monitoring: Researchers", "Open Science monitoring: Institutions", "Open Science monitoring: Countries", "Open Science monitoring: general", "Data", "Other". The category "Data" is only applicable for services.

¹⁵ Non applicable for datasets, templates and guidelines.

¹⁶ "Narratives", "Indicators". "Lists of contributions", "Badges", "Other".

covered_research_products*	On which type of research products (articles, datasets, software, etc.) this resource focuses. In case of a dataset, does it provide (meta)data on different types of research products? If it is a guidance document does it provide guidelines for all types of products? User provided.	array of strings	required
temporal_coverage	The time period(s) covered by the resource. User provided.	text	optional

Equity & ethical considerations

This category of metadata captures information on the equity and ethical considerations of a resource

Field name	Short description	Data type	Requirement
privacy_policy	URL to the privacy compliance notice (a digital document of some kind) detailing the respective practices including GDPR and similar guidelines. User provided.	string - URL	recommended
limitations	Text describing known limitations of the resource (e.g., regarding coverage, quality of data, etc). User provided.	text	optional
ethical_considerations	Text describing related ethical considerations (e.g., known biases, etc). User provided.	text	optional
ethics_committee	List of people contributing as ethics advisors for the resource. User provided.	array of strings	optional

Statistics

Statistics related to the usage of the resource.

Field name	Short description	Data type	Requirement
downloads**	Resource downloads ¹⁷ (all versions). Can be fetched from Zenodo (stats.downloads).	integer	N/A
udownloads**	Resource unique downloads ¹⁸ (all versions). Can be fetched from	integer	N/A

¹⁷ Not applicable for services.

¹⁸ Not applicable for services.

	Zenodo (stats.unique_downloads).		
views**	Resource views ¹⁹ (all versions). Can be fetched from Zenodo (stats.views).	integer	N/A
uviews**	Resource unique views ²⁰ (all versions). Can be fetched from Zenodo (stats.unique_views).	integer	N/A
version_downloads**	Resource downloads ²¹ (most recent version). Can be fetched from Zenodo (stats.version_downloads).	integer	N/A
version_udownloads**	Resource unique downloads ²² (most recent version). Can be fetched from Zenodo (stats.version_unique_downloads).	integer	N/A
version_views**	Resource views ²³ (most recent version). Can be fetched from Zenodo (stats.version_views).	integer	N/A
version_uviews**	Resource unique views ²⁴ (most recent version). Can be fetched from Zenodo (stats.version_unique_views).	integer	N/A
times_cited**	The number of times the resource was cited ²⁵ either directly or via the main article introducing it. Can be fetched from the OpenAIRE Graph.	integer	N/A

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¹⁹ Views=accesses for services.

²⁰ Views=accesses for services.

²¹ Not applicable for services.

²² Not applicable for services.

²³ Views=accesses for services.

²⁴ Views=accesses for services.

²⁵ Not applicable for services.